

VIRUSLI GEPATIT VA JIGARNING SURUNKALI KASALLIKLARI BILAN OG‘RIGAN BEMORLARDA OVQATLANISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada virusli gepatit va jigarning surunkali kasalliklari bilan og‘rigan bemorlarda kasallik davrini hisobga olib ovqatlanish to‘g‘risida ma’lumot berilgan.

Annotatsiya. V state predstavlena informatsiya o pitanii bolnyx virusnymi gepatitami i xronicheskimi zabolevaniyami pecheni s uchetom perioda zabolevaniya.

Annotation: There are given information about patients nutrition who had steady liver illnesses and viral hepatitis at their diseased time in this article.

Kalit so‘zlar: Virusli gepatit, parxez, sutli bo‘tqa, meva va sabzavotlar, sharbatlar, yog‘siz go‘sht, jigar hujayrasi.

Klyuchivye slova: Virusnyy gepatit, diyeta, molochnaya kasha, frukty i ovoцы, soki, obezjirenoye myaso, kletka pecheni.

Key words: Viral hepatitis, diet, milky porridge, fruits and vegetables, juices, ungreasy meat, liver cellar.

Virusli gepatit va jigarning surunkali kasalliklarida diyetoterapiya asosiy vazifasi distrofik o‘zgarishlarning kamayishiga imkon beradi. Surunkali virusli gepatitlar bilan og‘rigan bemorlar to‘g‘ri ovqatlanishlari, imkoni boricha uy taomlaridan iste’mol qilish, ko‘proq xo‘l mevalar tavsiya etiladi. Ovqatlanish 4 marta, oz-ozdan bo‘lishi kerak. Ovqat tayinlashda kasallik davrini hisobga olish zarur. [1,2,3,4].

Qand bola gavdasi og‘irligining 1 kg ga 5 g, mevalar 300—500 g hisobidan tayyorlanadi. Suyuqlikni yetarlicha berish, u 5% glyukoza, suv, choy, suyultirilgan meva sharbatlari ko‘rinishida bo‘lishi kerak. [9,11]. So‘ngra bola ovqatiga sabzavot qaynatmasi, kisel, sutli bo‘tqa, sabzavot, meva sharbatlarini kiritish mumkin. Ishtaxa yaxshilangan sayin ovkat xajmi oshirib boriladi. Toksikoz kamayganda, umumiy ahvol va ishtaha yaxshilanganda maxsulotlar va taomlar xili kengaytiriladi, ovqatga sabzavot va go‘sht pyuresi, bo‘tqa, kefir, kisel kabilar kiritiladi. Meva va

sabzavotlar sharbatlar ko‘rinishida beriladi. Keyinroq 5-parhezga o‘tkaziladi. Unda tvorog va sut maxsulotlari xisobiga lipotrop moddalar miqdori birmuncha oshiriladi. Taomlar qaynatilgan va qirilgan xolda tayyorlangani tufayli me‘da va ichakning mexanik ta’sirlanishi kamayadi, ovqat xazmi yaxshilinadi. Bir kun avval yopilgan bug‘doy non beriladi, yog‘siz go‘sht va baliq pyure ko‘rinishida bug‘da tayyorlab beriladi. Dag‘al kletchatkali va ichni dam qiladigan sabzavotlar (karam, turp, rediska) chiqariladi. Tuxum asosan bug‘da pishgan omlet ko‘rinishida beriladi. Nordonmas mevalar pechda pishirilib yoki qaynatib beriladi. Kasallikning o‘tkir davri o‘tib bo‘lgach bolaning axvoli qoniqarli bo‘lganda mexanik extiyotlash darajasini kamaytirish mumkin. U stasionardan chiqqandan keyin 6 oygacha parhez qiladi, bu muddat ba‘zan 1 yilgacha uzaytirilishi mumkin. Bu parhez organizmdagi metabolik jarayonlarga va organ parenximasiga ta’sir ko‘rsatadigan tadbirlar yig‘indisini qo‘llanishdan iborat. Jigarining surunkali kasalliklarida (surunkali gepatit, tsirroz) xam 5-sonli parhez ayrim o‘zgarishlar bilan tayinlanadi. Virusli gepatitlarda belgilanadigan parhezning asosini tashkil qiladigan uglevodlar miqdori keskin kamaytiriladi, chunki uglevodlarning ortiqcha buyurilishi lipogenez jarayonini kuchaytirib, jigarda yog‘ to‘planishiga sabab bo‘lishi mumkin. Jigar to‘qimasini tiklash jarayonlarini quvvatlash uchun patogenetik asoslangan diyetoterapiya qo‘llanish kerak bo‘ladi. [5,6,7,8]. Jarayonning faol davrida yog‘siz go‘sht va yog‘sizlantirilgan oqsilli enpitdan qo‘shimcha foydalanish xisobiga parhezda xayvonot oqsilini yosh normasiga nisbatan 15 foizga ko‘paytirish kerak. Oqsilga boy parhez yuqori lipotrop xossalarga ega. Bundan tashqari ko‘p miqdorda qand iste’moli o‘t ajralish funksiyasini bo‘g‘ib, og‘irlik davrining cho‘zilishiga olib keladi. Glyukokortikoid terapiya o‘tkazishda parhezdagi oqsil yosh normasiga nisbatan 30% va xatto 50% ga ko‘paytirilishi mumkin. [10,11,12]. Bunday bemorlar ovqatida oqsilning ko‘payishi oshgan ishtaxani qoniqtiradi, teri osti yog‘ kletchatkasida ortiqcha yog‘ to‘planishiga qisman to‘sqinlik qiladi. Bunda parhezga kaliy tuzlariga boy maxsulotlarni (pechda pishgan kartoshka, mayiz, o‘rik, va b.) kiritish lozim. [13,14,15]. Jigar sirrozining aktiv va aktivmas formasi bo‘lgan kupchilik bemorlarda ovqatda yog‘ chegaralanmaydi va ratsionga yosh normasi atrofida kiritiladi, bunda o‘simlik moyi miqdori ratsiondagi umumiy yog‘ miqdoridan 15 foizni tashkil qiladi. Jigar yetishmovchiligi yaqqol bo‘lganda ratsionda oqsil miqdori kamaytiriladi, jigar komasida esa uni batamom chiqarilib, keyin tegishli bioximiyaviy ko‘rsatkichlar nazorati ostida asta-sekin oshirib

boriladi. Jarayonning aktiv va aktivmas fazasida yog‘ni o‘simlik moyidan qo‘shimcha foydalanish xisobiga yosh normasiga nisbatan 15 foizga oshirish kerak. Parxezda yog‘ning oshirilishi taomlarning ta‘mini yaxshilaydi va ularning xilini ko‘paytiradi[15,16]

So‘nggi yillardagi tadqiqotlarda jarayonning aktiv fazasidagi bolalarda o‘simlik yog‘ining fiziologik normaga nisbatan 15 foizga ko‘paytirilishi jarayon aktivligining so‘nishiga olib kelganligi isbotlandi. Gepatobiliar sistemaning xronik kasalliklari vitaminlar yetishmasligi bilan o‘tadi. [17,18]. Shu maqsadda bolaga olma, limon va sabzi sharbati, har xil meva sharbatlari beriladi. So‘ngi yillarda bunday kasallikka uchragan bolalarga arpa, bug‘doy va makkajo‘xorining unib chiqqan donlarining polisolid ekstraktidan tayyorlangan yangi davo mahsulotlari qo‘llanilyapti, ular tarkibida biologik aktiv moddalar (mikroelementlar, vitaminlar, fitogormonlar) bo‘ladi. [19,20]. O‘t haydovchi giyohlar qo‘shib tayyorlangan xolesol shunday mahsulotlardan hisoblanadi. Xolesal biliar yo‘llarining funksional buzilishlari klinik kechishiga ijobiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi, lipidlar metabolizmini normaga soladi. Xolesol 5-10 yoshgacha bolalarga bir desert qoshiqdan kuniga 3 marta, 10-14 yoshgacha bir oshqoshiqdan kuniga 3 marta ovqatdan oldin tayinlanadi. Davolash kursi 3-4 hafta.

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